

Effect of 10 km run on lower limb skin temperature and thermal response after a cold-stress test over the following 24 h

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ABSTRACT

Skin temperature assessment has received much attention as a possible measurement of physiological response against stress produced by exercise and research studies usually measure skin temperature 24 or 48 h after exercise. Scientific evidence about skin temperature evolution during the 24-h period immediately after exercising is, however, scarce. The aim was to assess the effect of a 10 km run at moderate intensity on baseline skin temperature and thermal response after a cold stress test during that 24 h period. Fourteen participants were measured before, immediately after, and at 2, 5, 9 and 24 h after a 10 km run at a perceived exertion rate of 11 points (max 20 points). Fourteen control participants who undertook no exercise were also measured during that day. The measurements included muscle pain and fatigue perception, reactive oxygen species, heart rate variability, skin temperature of the lower limbs, and skin temperature after cold stress test. Exercise resulted in a skin temperature increase (e.g., 0.5–1.3 °C of posterior leg 9 h after exercise) and this effect continued in some regions (0.4–0.9 °C of posterior leg) over that 24 h period. However, the thermal response to the cold stress test remained the same ($p > 0.05$). In conclusion, 10 km aerobic running exercise results in a skin temperature increase, peaking at between 5 and 9 h after exercise, but does not alter the thermal response to a cold stress test. This study provides a sound basis for post-exercise skin temperature response that can be used as a setting-off point for comparisons with future studies that analyze greater muscle damage.

1. Introduction

The assessment of skin temperature to monitor muscle damage and physiological stress has gained attentions in recent years (Carvalho et al., 2021; de Andrade Fernandes et al., 2017; Priego-Quesada et al., 2020). Its foundations are based on the fact that muscle damage and tissue inflammation could increase muscle temperature and therefore increase skin temperature (Fernández-Cuevas et al., 2017; Hildebrandt et al., 2010). However, no skin temperature response has been observed 24 and 48 h after marathons (Priego-Quesada et al., 2020), half-marathons (Pérez-Guarner et al., 2019), or muscle damage induction protocol (Ferreira-Júnior et al., 2021). It has been suggested that delayed onset muscle soreness and muscle damage can cause peripheral vasoconstriction and be the cause of the lack of a clear effect on skin temperature (Priego-Quesada et al., 2020).

To arrive at these results, research studies usually measure baseline skin temperature before and 24/48 h after exercise (Carvalho et al., 2021; de Andrade Fernandes et al., 2017; Ferreira-Júnior et al., 2021; Priego-Quesada et al., 2020). However, the literature is scarce in terms of monitoring the effect of physical exercise over 24 h period immediately after exercise. Fernández-Cuevas et al. (2014) explored skin temperature responses in the 8 h period after exercise and observed a continuous increase of skin temperatures, with a peak at 6 h after strength and aerobic exercise. More studies are necessary to validate these results, with more physiological outcomes to explain skin response. Moreover, due to the possible effect of the circadian rhythm on skin temperature (Costa et al., 2016; Marins et al., 2015), control participants are needed to ensure that these increases are due to exercise and not due to the evolution of the day. One limitation of previous studies has been the absence of a control group, without which it is difficult to say whether skin temperature response is due to exercise or

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Abbreviations

β_0	constant coefficient of the logarithmic equation obtained for the skin temperature recovery after cold stress test
β_1	slope coefficient of the logarithmic equation obtained for the skin temperature recovery after cold stress test
ESd	Cohen effect sizes
ESr	Rosenthal's r effect sizes
FORT	free oxygen radical test
HF	high frequency component
Post	measurement performed immediately after finishing the exercise
Post2	measurement performed between 2 and 3 h after finishing the exercise
Post5	measurement performed between 4 and 6 h after finishing the exercise
Post9	measurement performed between 8 and 10 h after finishing the exercise
Post24	measurement performed 24 h after finishing the exercise
Pre	measurement performed before exercise
RMSSD	the root mean square of successive differences
ROIs	regions of interest
ROS	reactive oxygen species
SDNN	standard deviation of the NN interval
SDNN index	the mean of the standard deviation calculated over the windowed intervals

due to other factors (e.g. modifications of environmental temperature or circadian rhythm) (de Andrade Fernandes et al., 2017; Fernández-Cuevas et al., 2014). This type of research, with a control group, is necessary to better understand whether skin temperature measurements should be within some specific time window in order to monitor physiological stress or muscle damage (Priego-Quesada et al., 2020).

The cold stress test is a test commonly used in medical research that consists of cooling the skin to assess posterior vascularization capacity, often from the response of the skin temperature after cooling (Zaproudina et al., 2011). This type of test has been used to assess the severity of cold sensitivity (Eglin et al., 2017; House et al., 2015), and to detect the vascular dysfunction produced by pathologies such as hypertension (Greaney et al., 2017), diabetes (Zeng et al., 2016), or Raynaud pathology (Horikoshi et al., 2016), among others. However, its use to assess the effect of exercise is scarce. The cold stress test was, however, used to assess the effect of a marathon and greater drops in skin temperature in the posterior leg 24 h after the marathon were observed (Priego-Quesada et al., 2020). Exercise increases the levels of endothelial nitric oxide which can reduce blood vessel vasoconstriction (Perival, 2011), so suggesting a faster skin temperature recovery after a cold stress test. Therefore, it would be interesting to explore the effect of exercise on skin temperature rewarming after applying a cold stress test.

Previous studies suggest that the effect of exercise on skin temperature could differ depending on duration and intensity, or whether the exercise causes muscle damage or not (Hillen et al., 2020; Priego-Quesada et al., 2020). We, therefore, decided to focus this study on assessing a 10 km running aerobic exercise in which we expect low or not muscle damage with participants used to run this distance. The aim of this study was to determine the effect of a 10 km run at moderate perceived intensity, on baseline skin temperature and thermal response after a cold stress test over the 24 h period immediately following the run. Based on previous studies (Fernández-Cuevas et al., 2014; Priego-Quesada et al., 2020), it was hypothesized that skin temperature would be higher than in the control group after exercise and that there would be a greater

warming after cold stress in the measurements after exercise than before. Other physiological parameters such as Reactive oxygen species (ROS), heart rate variability parameters, and muscle pain/fatigue perception were measured to provide a characterization of the fatigue and parasympathetic activity (Laborde et al., 2017; Leung et al., 2004; Wan et al., 2017).

2. Material and methods

2.1. Participants

Experimental design consisted in an experimental and control group with intentional, prospective, and longitudinal sampling. Between 4 and 6 participants (half controls and the other half experimental participants) were measured in each two-day batch of measurements. In this sense, the study was carried out in 6 batches of measurements.

After assessing the skin temperature of the first four participants (two controls and two experimental), sample size of 14 participants per group was estimated for ANOVA repeated measures of 2 groups and 4 measurements with an effect size f of 0.45, a power of 95% and error of 5% (G*Power 3 software, University of Düsseldorf, Düsseldorf, Germany). Therefore, twenty-eight physically active participants volunteered to participate in the study, divided into experimental ($n = 14$, 6 females) and control ($n = 14$, 5 females) participants (Table 1). The study measurements were carried out on a military base. The reason for this was to make use of on-duty soldiers as control participants for their availability to carry out various measurements throughout the day. Hence, most of the participants were military (6 experimental and 14 controls), supplemented by non-military people for experimental participants. The recruitment of these non-military participants was performed by contacting with running clubs. Inclusion criteria included a history of a running training schedule of at least 3 running sessions/week in the past year and with at least one session of 10 km running at month. Exclusion criteria were a history of lower limb injuries within the last month, suffering from heart, neurological or musculoskeletal disorders affecting normal locomotion and to be taking medication that interferes with stability during running. All participants signed a written consent form and the study. This research protocol is in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Ethical Committee for Research in Humans of the University of Valencia. Instructions were provided to the participants to control the factors that can affect skin temperature: to avoid sunbathing, physiotherapy treatments and high intensity physical activity in the 24 h before the assessments, to avoid smoking, drinking alcohol, caffeine, or other stimulant beverages in the 12 h before the assessments, to avoid large meals, ointments, cosmetics, and other exercise other than that stipulated by the study during the day of measurements, and to sleep at least 7 h the day of the study. The participants confirmed their compliance with all these instructions. Moreover, all the female participants were tested during the luteal phase of the menstrual cycle.

Table 1
Sample characteristics of the two groups assessed (Control and Experimental).

	Experimental Mean \pm SD	Control Mean \pm SD	Exp vs. Control p-value (ESd)
N (females N)	14 (6)	14 (5)	–
Age (years)	35 \pm 9	36 \pm 5	0.86 (0.1)
Height (cm)	170.5 \pm 6.4	174.4 \pm 6.9	0.13 (0.6)
Body mass (kg)	67.7 \pm 10.2	74.9 \pm 10.0	0.07 (0.7)
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	23.2 \pm 2.5	25.2 \pm 3.5	0.09 (0.7)
Body fat (%)	18.1 \pm 7.1	20.3 \pm 6.8	0.41 (0.3)

Differences between groups were assessed with Student's t tests and Cohen effects sizes (ESd).

2.2. Design

Fig. 1 A shows the experimental design. The experimental group ran 10 km at a moderate rate of perceive exertion (11 points using the 20-point Borg scale) in an outdoor running track. Each participant ran with their own running clothing, all of them with shorts and short-sleeved t-shirt. The time taken for the 10 km was 49 ± 8 min. The Control group did not perform any exercise. A similar number of participants of each group were measured each measurement day. Measurements were performed before exercise between 7 a.m. and 9 a.m. (Pre), immediately after finishing the exercise (Post; only for the experimental group), between 2 and 3 h after exercise (Post2), between 4 and 6 h after exercise (Post5), between 8 and 10 h after exercise (Post9) and 24 h after exercise (Post24). In the Pre moment, body composition variables were obtained from the participants using a bioelectrical impedance system (Tanita BC-545N, Tanita Corp., Japan). For the Pre moment in which all the measurements were performed, the order was as follows: first, body composition, muscle pain and fatigue perception, and Reactive oxygen species were measured. After this, participants stood in an upright resting position (both men and women wearing only underpants and sports bra, being the same for each participant in all the measurement moments) for 10 min to adapt to the temperature of the room (Marins et al., 2014). During these 10 min, heart rate variability was recorded. Once the thermal room adaptation was completed, thermal images of the lower limbs were obtained (baseline skin temperature), before the participants underwent the cold stress test using an electronic cryotherapy system, and then thermal images were taken again for 3 min. At every moment of the protocol, heart rate variability, skin temperature of the lower limbs, and skin temperature after cold stress test were registered. ROS were obtained in the Pre and Post moments for experimental group, and in the Pre and Post2 for the control group; and muscle pain and fatigue perception

were measured in the Pre and Post24 moments.

Room temperature was controlled with an air-conditioning system and environmental conditions were recorded using a thermo-hygrometer with an accuracy of ± 1 °C and $\pm 3\%$ relative humidity (Digital thermo-hygrometer, TFA Dostmann, Germany). Environmental conditions at the different measurement moments were: Pre (19.6 ± 1.9 °C room temperature and $37 \pm 3\%$ of relative humidity), Post (19.6 ± 1.6 °C and $37 \pm 1\%$), Post2h (19.8 ± 1.9 °C and $36 \pm 3\%$), Post5h (19.9 ± 2.1 °C and $36 \pm 4\%$), Post9h (20.1 ± 1.0 °C and $38 \pm 2\%$) and Post24 h (19.4 ± 2.3 °C and $39 \pm 4\%$). In addition, the reflected temperature was measured using the standard method ISO 18434-1:2008, obtaining 1 °C more than the room temperature. This experimental phase took place during December and January, and therefore the mean, maximum and minimum environmental outdoor temperatures were 11.0 ± 0.7 °C, 15.4 ± 0.5 °C and 6.8 ± 0.4 °C (data from <https://es.climate-data.org/>).

2.3. Measurements

2.3.1. Muscle pain and fatigue perception

Muscle pain and fatigue perception were measured using a 150-mm visual analogue scale (Mündermann et al., 2002). Participants reported their perception for overall body and different body sites: trunk and upper limbs, buttocks, thigh, knee, leg and foot. The scales were labeled from the left as “absence of fatigue/pain” to the right as “highest fatigue/pain imaginable”. To increase the accuracy of the methodological process, each participant provided their perception at Post24 moment in the same visual analogue scale as they marked at the Pre measurement.

2.3.2. Reactive oxygen species

ROS were measured as biomarkers related to the duration and intensity of the exercise performed and its relationship with muscle fatigue

A. Experimental design

Groups measured	Exp Contr	Exp 	Exp	Exp Contr	Exp Contr	Exp Contr	Exp Contr
Measurements	PRE Pain/Fatig ROS Hrv Skt Skt-cold	EXERCISE 10Km	POST ROS Hrv Skt Skt-cold	POST2 ROS (only Contr) Hrv Skt Skt-cold	POST5 Hrv Skt Skt-cold	POST9 Hrv Skt Skt-cold	POST24 Pain/Fatig Hrv Skt Skt-cold

B. Regions of Interest

Fig. 1. A. Experimental design of the study: two groups were measured (Exp – experimental, Contr – Control) before running (PRE), post-running (POST) and 2 (POST2), 5 (POST5), 9 (POST9) and 24 h after running (POST24). The measurements performed were: Pain/fatigue – pain and fatigue perception, ROS – Reactive oxygen species, Hrv - heart rate variability, Skt – baseline skin temperature, and Skt-cold – skin temperature after a cold stress test of 3 min. B. The regions of interest for thermography measurements: (1) anterior thigh, (2) posterior thigh, (3) knee, (4) posterior knee, (5) anterior leg, and (6) posterior leg.

(Gomez-Cabrera et al., 2021; Wan et al., 2017). Due to the COVID situation, ROS were analyzed in a smaller number of participants. The reason for this was that the evaluator, who was in charge of performing the ROS analysis and had the measurement equipment in his possession, tested positive for COVID and could not attend two measurement days. Therefore, the sample for this analysis consisted of 10 experimental individuals and 12 controls.

ROS were assessed using the free oxygen radical test (FORT) from a single drop of capillary blood with a colorimetric assay (CR3000 analyzer, Callegari, the Catellani group, Italy) (Lewis et al., 2016; Pavlatou et al., 2009). FORT consists of applying an acidic buffer to the 20 μL capillary blood sample, releasing the transition metals ($\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$) from associated proteins, which react with the hydroperoxides present in the sample (R-OOH), producing the alkoxy (R-O^{\bullet}) and peroxy radicals (R-OO^{\bullet}) (Lewis et al., 2016). The derivative radicals are trapped by adding a buffered chromogen (reagent; an amine derivative, CrNH_2) and developing into a radical cation in a linear-based reaction at a controlled temperature of 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, photometrically detectable at 505 nm (Lewis et al., 2016).

2.3.3. Heart rate variability

Heart rate variability was measured as an indirect measure of parasympathetic activity (Laborde et al., 2017) and was registered using the Polar V800 (Polar Electro Oy, Finland) and analyzed using the “RHRV” package (Martínez et al., 2017) in RStudio. For the analysis, the last 3 min of the 10 min room adaptation was selected. After data filtering using the package’s automatic and manual methods, the time domain (using a window size of 60 s) and frequency domain (using the Fourier Transform) of heart rate variability was performed. Variables extracted were the Standard Deviation of the NN interval (SDNN), the mean of the Standard Deviation calculated over the windowed intervals (SDNN index), the Root Mean Square of Successive Differences (RMSSD), and the High Frequency component (HF). The percentage variation with regard to the Pre measurement moment was assessed (Laborde et al., 2017).

2.3.4. Skin temperature

Skin temperature was assessed using a thermal imaging camera (E60, Flir Systems Inc., USA) with a sensor array size of 320 \times 240, instantaneous field of view (IFOV) of 1.36 mrad, and noise equivalent temperature difference (NETD) of <50 mK and measurement uncertainty of ± 2 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ of the overall temperature reading. A Thermographic Imaging in Sports and Exercise Medicine checklist was used to corroborate that all the essential aspects of the thermographic protocol were attended to (Moreira et al., 2017). The camera was turned on 10 min before the measurements and it was positioned at 3 m from the participant. After taking the thermal images, obtained after 10 min of adaptation, the preferred lower limbs of the participants were cooled for 3 min using an electronic cryotherapy system (Game Ready GRPro 2.1, Cool Systems Inc., USA) while the participants were lying supine. Game Ready is a system that combines a control unit filled with ice and water that pumps the water constantly to the circumferential wraps (by ducts inserted into the tissue and therefore without wetting the skin) to apply cold and intermittent pneumatic compression. The cryotherapy system was configured to the lowest temperature (between 0 and 3 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) with moderate pressure for the wrap (intermittent pneumatic compression between 5 and 50 mm Hg considering manufacturer information). The circumferential wrap used was the “full leg boot wrap” model for cooling the entire lower limb. Thermal images were then taken at 30, 60, 120, and 180 s after finishing the cold stress protocol.

The mean temperature of the 6 Regions of Interest (ROIs) of the lower limb (Fig. 1B) was obtained using thermography software (Thermacam Researcher Pro 2.10 software, FLIR, Wilsonville, Oregon, USA). Emissivity was set at 0.98 (Moreira et al., 2017; Steketee, 1973). For the cold stress test data (skin temperature recovery during the 3 min after finishing cooling), a logarithmic equation for each ROI was

calculated, and constant (β_0) and slope (β_1) coefficients were obtained (Priego-Quesada et al., 2020):

$$\text{Skin temperature variation (}^{\circ}\text{C)} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \ln(\text{time after the cold stress test (s)})$$

The mean \pm SD of the R^2 of the equations obtained shows their adjustment: anterior thigh 0.95 ± 0.06 , posterior thigh 0.97 ± 0.03 , knee 0.93 ± 0.06 , posterior knee 0.97 ± 0.04 , anterior leg 0.97 ± 0.03 , and posterior leg 0.98 ± 0.02 .

For the mean baseline skin temperature and coefficients of the logarithmic equations, variations were calculated as the difference between each moment and the Pre measurement moment.

2.4. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using RStudio (version 1.2.5033). The normality of the variables was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Muscle pain and fatigue perception, ROS, and heart rate variability variables presented a non-normal distribution ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, difference with the Pre measurement moment was assessed for all the variables and for each group using Wilcoxon tests with Bonferroni correction. For skin temperature variation, repeated-measures analysis of variance with Bonferroni post hoc test were applied for each ROI with 2 intra-subject factors (measurement moment and leg preference), and one inter-subject factor (group). The same analysis was performed for variation between the coefficients of the logarithmic equation but without the leg preference factor. Significance level was set at $p < 0.05$. Cohen effect sizes (ESd) were calculated for pair significant differences of parametrical data and classified as small (0.2–0.5), moderate (0.5–0.8), or large (>0.8) (Cohen, 1988). For non-parametrical data, Rosenthal’s r was calculated (ESr) and classified as small (0.1–0.3), moderate (0.3–0.5), or large (>0.5) (Rosenthal and Rubin, 2003). 95% confidence interval (95%CI) of the differences was also applied. To perform an exploratory analysis of the relationship between skin temperature evolution and the other physiological outcomes, Pearson’s correlation coefficient analysis was undertaken. To avoid an excessive repetition of statistical tests that can lead to an increase in the probability of error type I, variables were selected based on the results of the previous analysis. Significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) were classified as weak ($0.2 < |r| < 0.5$), moderate ($0.5 \leq |r| < 0.8$), or strong ($|r| \geq 0.8$) (O’Rourke et al., 2005).

3. Results

3.1. Effect of exercise on baseline skin temperature and its response after cold stress test

Because the statistical analysis has been carried out with temperature variations, Table 2 shows the values at the pre moment to describe the starting point of each group. The main effect of leg preference was not significant in the variation of baseline mean skin temperature ANOVAs ($p > 0.05$), nor was its interaction with the other factors. Therefore, this factor was not considered in the following results. Fig. 2 shows the evolution of baseline skin temperature. With regard to Pre measurement, the control group presented higher skin temperature at Post5 for anterior leg (95%CI [0.2, 0.7 $^{\circ}\text{C}$], $p = 0.02$ and ESd = 0.7) and

Table 2
Mean \pm SD of the absolute skin temperatures at the Pre moment.

	Experimental	Control
Anterior thigh	28.3 \pm 1.6	28.4 \pm 1.7
Knee	27.7 \pm 1.5	28.3 \pm 1.8
Anterior leg	29.4 \pm 1.2	30.2 \pm 1.2
Posterior thigh	28.8 \pm 1.7	29.1 \pm 1.7
Posterior knee	29.7 \pm 1.3	30.1 \pm 1.6
Posterior leg	29.0 \pm 1.4	29.7 \pm 1.5

Fig. 2. Mean and 95%CI of the variation of baseline skin temperature (ΔT). Different symbols were used: differences with the Pre moment (control group: # $p < 0.05$, ## $p < 0.01$ and ### $p < 0.001$; experimental group: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ and *** $p < 0.001$), and differences between groups († $p < 0.05$, †† $p < 0.01$ and ††† $p < 0.001$). Letters are used to show the Cohen effect size (S – small effect size, M – moderate effect size, L - large effect size).

at Post9 for anterior thigh (95%CI [0.6, 1.5 °C], $p < 0.01$ and $ESd = 0.9$), posterior thigh (95%CI [0.5, 1.3 °C], $p < 0.01$ and $ESd = 0.8$) and posterior knee (95%CI [0.3, 0.8 °C], $p < 0.01$ and $ESd = 0.9$). However, the experimental group had a higher skin temperature after Post measurement, and presented greater increases than the control group for most of the ROIs (e.g., experimental vs. control at Post9: knee 95%CI [0.1, 1.4 °C], $p = 0.03$ and $ESd = 0.4$; anterior leg 95%CI [0.3, 1.1 °C], $p < 0.001$ and $ESd = 0.6$; posterior knee 95%CI [0.2, 0.9 °C], $p < 0.01$ and $ESd = 0.9$; and posterior leg 95%CI [0.5, 1.3 °C], $p < 0.001$ and $ESd = 0.6$). Moreover, skin temperature was higher at Post24 than at Pre moment, with higher increases than the control group for the anterior leg (Pre vs Post 24 95%CI [0.2, 0.9 °C], $p < 0.01$ and $ESd = 0.6$; control vs experimental 95%CI [0.2, 1.1 °C], $p < 0.01$ and $ESd = 0.8$), posterior knee (Pre vs Post 24 95%CI [0.2, 0.7 °C], $p < 0.01$ and $ESd = 0.6$; control vs experimental 95%CI [0.3, 1.1 °C], $p < 0.01$ and $ESd = 0.9$) and posterior leg (Pre vs Post 24 95%CI [0.4, 0.9 °C], $p < 0.001$ and $ESd = 0.9$; control vs experimental 95%CI [0.4, 1.1 °C], $p < 0.001$ and $ESd = 1.1$).

Table 3 shows the coefficients of the logarithmic equations obtained

Table 3

Mean \pm SD of the coefficients of the logarithmic equations obtained with the cold stress test at Pre moment: Skin temperature variation ($^{\circ}C$) = $\beta_0 + \beta_1 * \ln(\text{time after the cold stress test (s)})$.

	Experimental		Control	
	β_0	β_1	β_0	β_1
Anterior thigh	-11.5 \pm 3.8	1.4 \pm 0.6	-11.6 \pm 3.0	1.4 \pm 0.4
Knee	-10.1 \pm 2.0	1.2 \pm 0.3	-11.2 \pm 3.8	1.3 \pm 0.5
Anterior leg	-10.7 \pm 2.5	1.4 \pm 0.4	-10.3 \pm 2.4	1.3 \pm 0.4
Posterior thigh	-16.2 \pm 2.0	1.9 \pm 0.4	-15.3 \pm 2.8	1.8 \pm 0.4
Posterior knee	-12.3 \pm 3.1	1.6 \pm 0.4	-11.9 \pm 2.9	1.5 \pm 0.5
Posterior leg	-14.7 \pm 1.8	1.8 \pm 0.3	-15.0 \pm 2.7	1.9 \pm 0.4

after the cold stress test at the moment Pre. Coefficients did not vary with regard to the Pre moment in each of the groups, and no differences were observed between groups at any measurement moment ($p > 0.05$) (Fig. 3).

3.2. Effect of exercise on physiological outcomes

Muscle pain and fatigue perception did not differ between moments in any of the groups and regions, except in the overall pain of the experimental group that presented stronger pain at Post24 than at Pre (0.2 ± 0.5 vs. 0.8 ± 0.9 cm, 95%CI of the difference between moments [0.2, 0.9 cm], $p = 0.02$ and $ESr = 0.4$). Mean pain values of the different regions without differentiating between groups and moments were: overall 0.5 ± 0.8 cm, trunk and upper limbs 0.6 ± 1.1 cm, buttocks 0.5 ± 1.0 cm, thigh 0.5 ± 0.9 cm, knee 1.1 ± 2.3 cm, and leg and foot 1.1 ± 2.1 cm. Mean fatigue values were: overall 1.2 ± 1.8 cm, trunk and upper limbs 0.6 ± 1.3 cm, buttocks 0.7 ± 1.3 cm, thigh 1.0 ± 1.9 cm, knee 1.0 ± 1.9 cm, and leg and foot 1.6 ± 2.6 cm.

While ROS were similar between Pre and Post2 moments in the control group (Pre vs. Post: 1.7 ± 0.4 vs. 1.8 ± 0.6 mmol/L H_2O_2 , $p = 0.7$), the experimental group presented lower values of ROS after exercise (Pre vs. Post: 1.8 ± 0.5 vs. 1.6 ± 0.5 mmol/L H_2O_2 , 95%CI [0.0, 0.4 mmol/L H_2O_2], $p = 0.02$ and $ESr = 0.2$).

Regarding heart rate variability (Fig. 4), no differences between measurement moments were observed in any of the variables for the control group ($p > 0.05$). However, the experimental group presented a significant percentage reduction at Post of the SDNN (95%CI [27.9, 55.6%], $p < 0.01$ and $ESr = 0.9$), SDNN index (95%CI [27.2, 57.5%], $p < 0.01$ and $ESr = 0.8$), RMSSD (95%CI [40.8, 69.4%], $p < 0.01$ and $ESr = 0.9$) and HF (95%CI [54.5, 86.4%], $p < 0.01$ and $ESr = 0.9$), and at Post2 of the SDNN (95%CI [29.8, 51.1%], $p < 0.01$ and $ESr = 0.9$), SDNN index (95%CI [26.9, 50.3%], $p < 0.01$ and $ESr = 0.9$), and RMSSD (95%CI [33.3, 60.9%], $p < 0.01$ and $ESr = 0.9$).

Fig. 3. Mean and 95%CI of the variation of the coefficients of the logarithmic equations obtained with the cold stress test: Skin temperature variation ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) = $\beta_0 + \beta_1 * \ln(\text{time after the cold stress test (s)})$. No differences were observed with the Pre moment in each group, and between groups at any measurement moment ($p > 0.05$).

Fig. 4. Mean and 95%CI of the variation (Δ) of heart rate variables (SDNN - standard deviation of the NN interval, SDNN index - mean of the standard deviation calculated over the windowed intervals, RMSSD - root mean square of successive differences, and HF - high frequency component). Differences with the Pre moment are showed using symbol (** $p < 0.01$) and letter (L - large effect size; Rosenthal's r).

3.3. Correlations between skin temperature and other physiological outcomes

Based on the results of section 3.1, it was decided to select the thermal data (variation of baseline mean skin temperature and

logarithmic coefficients) of the posterior leg at Post5 and Post24 moments for correlation analysis. For muscle pain and fatigue perception, overall, leg and foot regions were selected. For heart rate variability outcomes, RMSSD and HF were the variables selected as representative.

Variation of baseline posterior leg skin temperature presented a

weak positive correlation with fatigue perception ($r = 0.49$) at Post5, and an inverse weak-moderate correlation with heart rate variability at Post5 and Post24 (r between -0.43 and -0.55) (Table 4). No significant correlations were observed between variation of the coefficients of logarithmic equations and the variation of the other physiological outcomes ($p > 0.05$).

4. Discussion

The aim of this study was to assess the effect of a 10 km run at moderate perceived intensity on baseline skin temperature and thermal response after a cold stress test over a 24 h period immediately after that run. The main results were that, although the control group presented an increase of baseline skin temperature of lower limbs during the day, the experimental group presented higher increases with an effect that was maintained 24 h after undertaking exercise in the anterior and posterior leg, and posterior knee ROIs. However, the coefficients of logarithmic equations of the thermal response after cold stress test were unaltered. Finally, weak correlation was observed between the variation in fatigue perception and variation in baseline posterior leg skin temperature 5 h after exercise, and an inverse weak-moderate correlation of this ROI with the variation in heart rate variability 5 and 24 h after exercise.

The analysis of the effect of exercise on baseline temperatures was carried out in previous studies 24 or 48 h after the exercise (Carvalho et al., 2021; de Andrade Fernandes et al., 2017; Ferreira-Júnior et al., 2021; Priego-Quesada et al., 2020). In this sense, there is a lack of studies monitoring skin temperature over the 24 h period immediately following the exercise. The results of the present study showed that the experimental group presented a higher increase than the control group for the exercise undertaken, with a peak between 5 and 9 h after exercise, agreeing with a previous study (Fernández-Cuevas et al., 2014). Heat generated during exercise or by other processes such as glycogen resynthesis or increase in systemic hormones (Naperalsky et al., 2010;

West et al., 2010), could be dissipated by the increase of skin blood flow after exercise (Johnson and Kellogg, 2010; Kenny et al., 2008), resulting in a higher skin temperature. Moreover, the lower parasympathetic activity and, therefore, the higher sympathetic activation showed by the heart rate variability analysis immediately after and 2 h after exercise, could be related with a peripheral blood flow and so explain the increase in skin temperature in the first hours following exercise (Barnea and Shusterman, 1995). A time window between 5 and 9 h after exercise seems to be the ideal one for measuring the effect of exercise with low muscle damage. Future studies could assess the effect of different types of exercise on skin temperature recovery within this time window.

While skin temperature 24 h after exercise has been observed as increasing after soccer matches (de Andrade Fernandes et al., 2017), others studies present an unaltered variation (Ferreira-Júnior et al., 2021; Pérez-Guarner et al., 2019; Priego-Quesada et al., 2020). One hypothesis suggested was a curvilinear inverted U relationship between internal load and skin temperature responses (Priego-Quesada et al., 2020). This hypothesis is based on the findings of previous research studies stating that exercise without causing muscle damage or pain can lead to increases in baseline temperatures, while pain or muscle damage could increase peripheral vasoconstriction with no skin temperature variation (Priego-Quesada et al., 2020). The results of the current study, that suggest that the exercise performed was not enough to produce pain or muscle damage, appear to agree with this hypothesis. Low ratings of muscle pain perception were observed 24 h after exercise (0.5 ± 0.8 cm of visual analogue scale of 15 cm) compared with previous studies assessing a half-marathon (~ 5 cm) (Pérez-Guarner et al., 2019) or marathon competition (~ 5 cm) (Priego-Quesada et al., 2020). Moreover, the ROS values observed after exercise (1.6 ± 0.5 mmol/L H₂O₂) were in line with the other values reported by healthy individuals (≤ 2.3 mmol/L H₂O₂) (Gáman et al., 2020) and lower than those for 30 min of running at 80% of the maximum heart rate (2.5–2.8 mmol/L H₂O₂) (Quinn et al., 2021). Therefore, the reduction of ROS values observed suggests that ROS generation was lower than antioxidant generation (Gomez-Cabrera et al., 2021). Finally, intensity was inversely correlated by previous studies with the time and frequency domains of heart rate variability (Cornelissen et al., 2010; Hunt and Saengsuwan, 2018). Therefore, the direct moderate association between skin temperature variation 5 h after exercise with fatigue perception 24 h after exercise, the inverse association with heart rate variability, and the non-association between muscle pain perception and skin temperature, could be suggesting that the increase in training load, without reporting delayed onset muscle soreness, results in an increase in skin temperature. If this hypothesis is true, a future study replicating the current design but causing higher muscle damage should present similar values for skin temperature between the pre and 24 h post-exercise period associated with local vasoconstriction.

Previous studies have shown how skin temperature rewarming after a cold stress test was reduced by pathologies with vascular response impairment (Greaney et al., 2017; Horikoshi et al., 2016; Zeng et al., 2016), while pathologies with a higher metabolic rate such as breast cancer or hyperthyroidism resulted in faster rewarming (Amri et al., 2016; Jin et al., 2014). However, contrary to what had been hypothesized, in general, no alteration of the thermal response to the cold stress test was observed after exercising. This could mean that the exercise performed was not sufficient to alter the capacity of the vascular response. Greater skin temperature reduction following cold stress (lower β_0) has been observed in the posterior leg 24 h after a marathon, so suggesting a higher peripheral vasoconstriction state of the athletes (Priego-Quesada et al., 2020). However, contrary to what had been hypothesized, no alteration of the thermal response to the cold stress test was observed after exercising. This could mean that the exercise performed was not sufficient to alter the capacity of the vascular response. All these results should encourage further studies to analyze how muscle damage or different running intensities can affect thermal response to a cold stress test.

Table 4

Pearson's correlation coefficients (r) between the variation of baseline mean skin temperature (ΔT) and coefficients of the logarithmic equations ($\Delta\beta_0$ and $\Delta\beta_1$) of the posterior leg corresponding of thermal response after the cold stress test, and the variation percentage of the other outcomes in all participants.

	ΔT		$\Delta\beta_0$		$\Delta\beta_1$	
	r	p	r	p	r	p
Post 5						
Δ Post24 Pain leg and foot	0.08	0.69	-0.03	0.90	0.01	0.94
Δ Post24 Pain overall	0.29	0.15	-0.34	0.09	0.37	0.06
Δ Post24 Fatigue leg and foot	0.49	0.01	0.15	0.46	-0.15	0.47
Δ Post24 Fatigue overall	0.49	0.01	0.14	0.48	-0.12	0.54
Δ Post5 RMSSD	-0.55	0.00	-0.20	0.32	0.07	0.72
Δ Post5 HF	-0.45	0.02	-0.19	0.36	0.06	0.79
Δ Post RMSSD	-0.43	0.03	-0.15	0.46	0.04	0.85
Δ Post HF	-0.51	0.01	-0.11	0.60	0.05	0.81
Δ Post ROS	-0.08	0.75	-0.15	0.54	0.08	0.72
Post 24						
Δ Post24 Pain leg and foot	0.11	0.59	0.07	0.72	-0.09	0.67
Δ Post24 Pain overall	0.19	0.35	0.05	0.82	-0.04	0.85
Δ Post24 Fatigue leg and foot	0.12	0.55	0.06	0.77	-0.14	0.49
Δ Post24 Fatigue overall	0.26	0.20	-0.04	0.83	-0.13	0.53
Δ Post24 RMSSD	-0.45	0.02	0.13	0.52	0.00	0.99
Δ Post24 HF	-0.25	0.22	0.05	0.79	0.05	0.80
Δ Post RMSSD	-0.55	0.00	-0.19	0.36	0.30	0.14
Δ Post HF	-0.50	0.01	-0.09	0.67	0.18	0.39
Δ Post ROS	-0.04	0.87	-0.31	0.18	0.30	0.19

Note: Δ Post24 – variation between 24 h post exercise and pre measurement moment; Δ Post5 – variation between 5 h post exercise and pre measurement moment; Δ Post – variation between post exercise and pre measurement moment; RMSSD – root mean square of successive differences of heart rate variability; HF – high frequency component of heart rate variability; ROS – Reactive oxygen species.

Circadian rhythm has been suggested as an important factor of influence on skin temperature (Costa et al., 2016; Marins et al., 2015). A previous study observed ~ 1 °C higher skin temperatures in the afternoon than in the morning in thigh and legs (Marins et al., 2015). Daily activities and changes in metabolic rate increase core temperature resulting in higher skin blood flow, which may explain circadian variations (Marins et al., 2015; Smolander et al., 1993). The results of the control group are in agreement with these previous studies, showing an increase of skin temperature in the afternoon (Post9) compared with the morning measurement (Pre) in some of the ROIs (anterior thigh, posterior thigh and posterior knee).

The main limitation of the study was that the lack of assessment of other physiological parameters that helped in the interpretation of the results, such as core and muscle temperature, skin blood flow, maximum oxygen consumption (for groups characterization), or creatine kinase. Another limitation was not having measured an antioxidative marker to understand better the ROS decrease. Moreover, the low sample size for women did not allow us to study the sex effect on the results. Finally, although instructions were provided to the participants to avoid confounding factors, and even if they reported their compliance, we cannot be sure that some participants did not follow all of the instructions.

5. Conclusion

10 km running aerobic exercise results in a posterior baseline skin temperature increase, peaking between 5 and 9 h after exercise. This type of exercise does not clearly alter the thermal response to a cold stress test. This study, therefore, provides a sound basis for post-exercise skin temperature response that can be used as a setting-off point for comparisons with future studies that analyze greater muscle damage.

Authors contribution

JIPQ, RCOA and RSP had the conceptualization of the idea. JIPQ, MTPC and AEM obtained the funding for the project. All the authors contributed to the design of the study. JIPQ, ICV, JLBR, AGS, MTPC performed the experiments and worked in the data curation. JIPQ performed the statistical analysis and the data visualization. AEM, RCOA and RSP supervised the project. JIPQ wrote the original draft of the manuscript, and all authors reviewed, edited, and agreed to the final version of the manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The author(s) declare no competing interests.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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